

Supplemental Materials

I. DERIVATION OF MOMENTUM AND ENERGY EQUATIONS FOR AN EXPANDING SHELL

This section presents a detailed derivation of the fundamental equations governing the evolution of an expanding thin shell, as introduced in Section 2 of the main text. Previously, Hayasaki & Yamazaki (2023) [1] investigated the evolution of an expanding shell driven by TDE disk winds in non-relativistic, radio-emitting TDEs. Their analysis was based on solving the momentum conservation equation under the thin-shell approximation, where the shell width is assumed to be much smaller than its radius, following the framework established by Chevalier (1982) [2]. In this work, we extend their study by developing a more comprehensive framework that incorporates the set of momentum and energy conservation equations, explicitly accounting for the effects of SMBH gravity, time-dependent mass injection from the disk wind to the shell, ambient drag forces, thermal pressure, and radiative cooling. The thin shell approximation is a powerful tool for capturing the essential physical characteristics of the dynamics of the radio emitter.

The derivation consists of three steps. First, we enforce mass conservation between the disk wind and the expanding shell to obtain the total shell mass. Second, we derive the equation of motion for the shell radius, incorporating the effects of SMBH gravity, ambient drag, and momentum injection. Third, we derive the energy equation, explicitly including the contributions from thermal pressure and radiative cooling. In our model, a star is tidally disrupted by an SMBH, leading to the formation of an accretion disk prior to t_0 . The expanding thin shell is assumed to form at $t = t_0$. Hereafter, an overdot denotes a derivative with respect to time, as in $\dot{Q} = dQ/dt$ for an arbitrary physical quantity Q .

A. Expanding Shell Mass with SMBH Gravity and Time-Dependent Injection

We derive the shell mass by enforcing mass conservation between the disk wind and the shell, accounting for both continuous injection and ambient mass sweep-up. A wind element launched at an earlier time t' ($t_0 < t' < t$) leaves the disk at radius r_0 and reaches radius r at time t [1]. Solving the equation of motion of the mass element moving under SMBH gravity along the radial direction, we obtain

$$\dot{r} = \sqrt{\frac{2GM_{\text{bh}}}{r}}, \quad (1)$$

where the initial velocity corresponds to the escape velocity at r_0 from the SMBH gravity as

$$v_0 = \sqrt{\frac{2GM_{\text{bh}}}{r_0}}. \quad (2)$$

We assume that the disk wind starts blowing at r_0 under the SMBH gravity with velocity \dot{r} . Integrating equation (1) from t' to t yields

$$r = r_0 \left[1 + \frac{3}{2} \frac{v_0}{r_0} (t - t') \right]^{2/3}, \quad (3)$$

where equation (2) are used for the derivation. The farthest radius that the wind's mass element can reach is then estimated to be

$$r_{\text{max}} = r_0 \left[1 + \frac{3}{2} \frac{v_0}{r_0} (t - t_0) \right]^{2/3} \quad (4)$$

at $t' = t_0$. Since the mass emitted at $t = t' + \Delta t'$ reaches the radius $r - \Delta r$, we obtain the following relation using equation (3) as

$$\Delta r = \dot{r} \Delta t'. \quad (5)$$

We also rewrite equation (3) as

$$t' = t + \frac{2}{3} \frac{r_0}{v_0} \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right]. \quad (6)$$

The thin shell is expected to form at $t = t_0$ due to the interaction between ambient matter and the disk wind. Subsequently, the disk wind dynamically impacts the shell, injecting mass over time. We assume that the mass injection rate from the disk wind follows a power-law decay after the formation of the shell, expressed as

$$\dot{M}_{\text{inj}}(t) = \dot{M}_0 \left(\frac{t}{t_0} \right)^{-n} \quad (7)$$

for $t \geq t_0$, where n is the power-law index. In our scenario, the mass injection rate is assumed to scale with the mass fallback rate [3]. Specifically, we adopt that $n = 5/3$ [4, 5] and

$$\dot{M}_0 = \frac{f}{3} \frac{m_*}{t_{\text{mtb}}},$$

where m_* is the stellar mass, f is the fractional parameter with $f = 0.1$ as its typical value, and

$$t_{\text{mtb}} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{M_{\text{bh}}}{m_*} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{r_*^3}{Gm_*} \right)^{1/2}$$

is the orbital period of the stellar debris on the most tightly bound orbit with the stellar radius r_* [6]. The total shell mass at coordinate time t equals the total mass launched in the wind at all earlier times $t' < t$. Each mass element propagates outward and reaches the shell after a finite travel time under the gravitational potential of the SMBH. Consequently, the injected mass is transferred one-to-one to the shell with a time delay, ensuring strict conservation of mass. The launch–arrival relation derived above links the current coordinate time t to its retarded time t' , thereby enabling computation of the unshocked ejecta density $\rho_{\text{ej}}(r, t)$ via the following continuity equation:

$$\dot{M}_{\text{inj}}(t') \Delta t' = 4\pi r^2 \Delta r \rho_{\text{ej}}(r, t), \quad (8)$$

which yields

$$\rho_{\text{ej}}(r, t) = \rho_{\text{ej},0} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-3/2} \left[\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left(1 - \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right) \right]^{-n}, \quad (9)$$

where equations (5)–(8) are used for the derivation, ϵ is defined as the dimensionless velocity parameter

$$\epsilon = \frac{r_0}{t_0 v_0}, \quad (10)$$

and the initial ejecta density $\rho_{\text{ej},0}$ is given by

$$\rho_{\text{ej},0} = \frac{\dot{M}_0}{4\pi r_0^2 v_0} = \epsilon \frac{M_0}{4\pi r_0^3}, \quad (11)$$

with $M_0 \equiv \dot{M}_0 t_0$. The ejecta mass comprising the infinitesimally thin shell at the radius $R(t)$ is then obtained by using equations (4), (9), and (11) as

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\text{ej}}(t) &= \int_{R(t)}^{r_{\text{max}}} 4\pi r^2 \rho_{\text{ej}}(r, t) dr \\ &= \frac{M_0}{n-1} \left[1 - \left(\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left[1 - \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right] \right)^{1-n} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The time derivative of equation (12) is given by

$$\dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t) = \dot{M}_0 \left[1 - \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{v_0} \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{1/2} \right] \left[\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left[1 - \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right] \right]^{-n}. \quad (13)$$

This is positive because $R(t) < v_0 t$ and $\dot{R}(t) < v_0$, meaning that the ejecta mass increases with time.

Next, we assume that the ambient matter density follows the power-law of radius distribution:

$$\rho_{\text{am}}(r) = \rho_{\text{am},0} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-s}, \quad (14)$$

where s is the power-law index and $\rho_{\text{am},0}$ is defined by using equation (11) as

$$\rho_{\text{am},0} = \epsilon\eta \frac{M_0}{4\pi r_0^3} \quad (15)$$

with a density ratio parameter η , defined as follows:

$$\eta = \frac{\rho_{\text{am},0}}{\rho_{\text{ej},0}}. \quad (16)$$

Integrating equation (14) from r_0 to $R(t)$, we obtain the shell mass, to which is contributed from the ambient matter, as

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\text{am}}(t) &= \int_{r_0}^{R(t)} \rho_{\text{am}}(r) dr \\ &= \frac{\epsilon\eta}{3-s} M_0 \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3-s} \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_0}{R(t)} \right)^{3-s} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where equations (15) and (16) are used for the derivation. The time derivative of equation (17) is given by

$$\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t) = \epsilon\eta \frac{M_0}{r_0} \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{2-s} \dot{R}(t). \quad (18)$$

The total mass of the thin shell at radius $R(t)$ is given by using equations (12) and (17) as

$$\begin{aligned} M(t) &= M_{\text{ej}}(t) + M_{\text{am}}(t) + \Delta m \\ &= \frac{M_0}{n-1} \left[1 + (n-1)\epsilon\delta - \left(\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left[1 - \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right] \right)^{1-n} \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{\epsilon\eta}{3-s} M_0 \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3-s} \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_0}{R(t)} \right)^{3-s} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where Δm represents the initial shell mass as

$$\Delta m = 4\pi\delta\rho_{\text{ej},0}r_0^3 = \delta\epsilon M_0, \quad (20)$$

δ is as a dimensionless parameter to decide the amount of Δm , and equation (11) is used for the derivation. The time derivative of equation (19) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{M}(t) &= \dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t) + \dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t) \\ &= \frac{2}{3}\dot{M}_0 \left[1 - \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{v_0} \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{1/2} \right] \left[\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left[1 - \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right] \right]^{-n} + \epsilon\eta \frac{M_0}{r_0} \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{2-s} \dot{R}(t). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

B. Momentum Conservation for an Expanding Shell under SMBH Gravity and External Forces

In this subsection, we derive the equation of motion by incorporating the effects of momentum injection from the ejecta, the gravitational influence of the SMBH, and external pressure forces. The momentum change of the shell due to an impulse $F(t)\Delta t$ applied over the interval t to $t + \Delta t$ is considered. By the principle of momentum conservation, we obtain

$$F(t)\Delta t = M(t + \Delta t)\dot{R}(t + \Delta t) - M(t)\dot{R}(t), \quad (22)$$

where $F(t)$ denotes the total force acting on the shell. Currently, $F(t)$ is composed of

$$F(t) = F_{\text{ej}}(t) + F_{\text{G}}(t) + F_{\text{th}}(t), \quad (23)$$

where

$$F_{\text{ej}}(t) = \dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t)\dot{r}(R(t)) \quad (24)$$

is the ram pressure force induced by the ejecta,

$$F_{\text{G}}(t) = -\frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M(t)}{R(t)^2} \quad (25)$$

is the gravitational force of the SMBH, and

$$F_{\text{th}}(t) = 4\pi R(t)^2 P(t) \quad (26)$$

represents the thermal pressure force acting on the shell due to the pressure in its inner region, respectively. The thermal pressure in the inner region is given by

$$P(t) = \chi(\gamma - 1)\frac{E_{\text{T}}(t)}{4\pi R(t)^2 \Delta R}, \quad (27)$$

where γ , the specific heat ratio, is set to $5/3$ for a monoatomic gas, χ is a dimensionless parameter of order unity arising from the thin-shell approximation, and ξ is the dimensionless shell thickness parameter, defined as

$$\xi = \frac{\Delta R}{R(t)}, \quad (28)$$

with a representative value of $\xi \approx 0.1$ [7].

Neglecting terms of order higher than the second in the Taylor series expansion of the right-hand side of equation (22) in the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ yields the following equation of motion:

$$\frac{d(M(t)\dot{R}(t))}{dt} = F(t).$$

Using equations (23)-(27), this equation can be rewritten as

$$M(t)\ddot{R}(t) = \dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t)\dot{r}(R(t)) - \dot{M}(t)\dot{R}(t) - \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M(t)}{R(t)^2} + \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi} \frac{E_{\text{T}}(t)}{R(t)}. \quad (29)$$

C. Energy Conservation with Heating and Cooling in an Expanding Shell

In this subsection, we derive the thermal energy evolution equation, explicitly incorporating the effects of thermal expansion, mass injection from the ejecta, and radiative cooling, assuming that the thermal energy is stored solely in the shell. We consider the energy conservation law before time t and after time $t + \Delta t$ for a system comprising the ejecta, the thin shell, and the ambient medium:

$$E_{\text{K}}(t) + E_{\text{T}}(t) + \Phi(t) + E_{\text{C}}(t) = E_{\text{K}}(t + \Delta t) + E_{\text{T}}(t + \Delta t) + \Phi(t + \Delta t) + E_{\text{C}}(t + \Delta t), \quad (30)$$

where E_{K} , E_{T} , Φ , and E_{C} represent the kinetic energy, thermal energy, gravitational potential energy, and the energy lost due to radiative cooling, respectively. The kinetic energy is given by

$$E_{\text{K}}(t) = \frac{1}{2}\Delta M_{\text{ej}}(t)\dot{r}^2(R(t)) + \frac{1}{2}M(t)\dot{R}(t)^2, \quad (31)$$

where ΔM_{ej} denotes the mass of the ejecta added due to a collision with the shell over the time interval Δt . After the collision between the ejecta and the shell, the energy is converted into the kinetic energy of the shell. The kinetic energy at $t + \Delta t$ is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{K}}(t + \Delta t) &= \frac{1}{2}M(t + \Delta t)\dot{R}(t + \Delta t)^2 \\ &\approx \frac{1}{2}M(t)\dot{R}^2(t) + M(t)\dot{R}(t)\ddot{R}(t)\Delta t + \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}(t)\dot{R}^2(t)\Delta t, \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where a Taylor series expansion is applied, retaining only terms up to first order in Δt . The temporal evolution of the other energy components E_{T} , Φ , and E_{C} over the time interval Δt can be expressed via a Taylor series expansion as

$$E_{\text{T}}(t + \Delta t) = E_{\text{T}}(t) + \dot{E}_{\text{T}}(t)\Delta t + \mathcal{O}(\Delta t^2), \quad (33)$$

$$\Phi(t + \Delta t) = \Phi(t) + \dot{\Phi}(t)\Delta t + \mathcal{O}(\Delta t^2), \quad (34)$$

$$E_{\text{C}}(t + \Delta t) = E_{\text{C}}(t) + \dot{E}_{\text{C}}(t)\Delta t + \mathcal{O}(\Delta t^2). \quad (35)$$

Substituting equations (31)–(35) into equation (30) and neglecting terms beyond second order in the Taylor expansion, we obtain the thermal energy gained over Δt as

$$\dot{E}_{\text{T}}(t)\Delta t = \frac{1}{2}\Delta M_{\text{ej}}(t)\dot{r}^2(R(t)) - M(t)\dot{R}(t)\ddot{R}(t)\Delta t - \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}(t)\dot{R}(t)^2\Delta t - \dot{\Phi}(t)\Delta t - \dot{E}_{\text{C}}(t)\Delta t.$$

Dividing both sides of the above equation by Δt and taking $\dot{M}_{\text{ej}} = \Delta M_{\text{ej}}/\Delta t$ in the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E}_{\text{T}}(t) &= \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t)\dot{r}^2(R(t)) - M(t)\dot{R}(t)\ddot{R}(t) - \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}(t)\dot{R}(t)^2 - \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M(t)}{R^2(t)}\dot{R}(t) \\ &\quad + \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}\dot{M}(t)}{R(t)} - \dot{E}_{\text{C}}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

where the gravitational potential energy is obtained from equation (25) as

$$\Phi(t) = \int_{R(t)}^{\infty} F_{\text{G}}(r) dr = -\frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M(t)}{R(t)}.$$

Substituting equation (29) into equation (36), we obtain the final expression for the thermal energy evolution:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E}_{\text{T}}(t) &= \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t)\left(\dot{r}(R(t)) - \dot{R}(t)\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t)\dot{R}^2(t) + \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}\dot{M}(t)}{R(t)} \\ &\quad - \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi}\frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R(t)}E_{\text{T}}(t) - \dot{E}_{\text{C}}(t). \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

D. Summary of the Basic Equations Governing an Expanding Thin Shell

The time evolution of the thin-shell radius, $R(t)$, is governed by equations (29) and (37), which also involve another time-dependent variable, the thermal energy $E_{\text{T}}(t)$. For completeness, we restate these equations below:

$$M(t)\ddot{R}(t) = \dot{M}_{\text{ej}}\dot{r}(R) - \dot{M}\dot{R}(t) - \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M(t)}{R^2(t)} + \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi}\frac{E_{\text{T}}(t)}{R(t)}, \quad (38)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E}_{\text{T}}(t) &= \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t)\left(\dot{r}(R(t)) - \dot{R}(t)\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t)\dot{R}^2(t) + \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}\dot{M}(t)}{R(t)} \\ &\quad - \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi}\frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R(t)}E_{\text{T}}(t) - \dot{E}_{\text{C}}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where equations (12), (13), and (17)–(21) specify the shell mass components and their time derivatives, as summarized below:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} M(t) = M_{\text{ej}}(t) + M_{\text{am}}(t) + \Delta m, \\ M_{\text{ej}}(t) = \frac{M_0}{n-1} \left[1 - \left(\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left[1 - \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right] \right)^{1-n} \right], \\ M_{\text{am}}(t) = \frac{\epsilon\eta}{3-s} M_0 \left[\left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3-s} - 1 \right], \\ \Delta m = \epsilon\delta M_0, \\ \dot{M}(t) = \dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t) + \dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t), \\ \dot{M}_{\text{ej}}(t) = \dot{M}_0 \left[1 - \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{v_0} \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{1/2} \right] \left[\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left[1 - \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right] \right]^{-n}, \\ \dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t) = \epsilon\eta \frac{M_0}{r_0} \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{2-s} \dot{R}(t). \end{array} \right. \quad (40)$$

II. ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTIONS FOR BASIC EQUATIONS

For a direct comparison with radio observations, we consider the time evolution of the shell at a position far from the SMBH. For $R(t) \gg r_0$ (or equivalently, $t \gg t_0$), the ejecta mass asymptotically approaches a constant value, given by

$$M_{\text{ej}}(t) = \frac{M_0}{n-1} \left[1 - \left(\frac{t}{t_0} + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon \left[1 - \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3/2} \right] \right)^{1-n} \right] \approx \frac{M_0}{|n-1|}, \quad (41)$$

where equation (12) has been used in the derivation. Equation (41) shows that equation (19) reduces to

$$M(t) \approx M_{\text{am}}(t) \quad (42)$$

for $R(t) \gg r_0$, since $M_{\text{am}}(t) \gg M_{\text{ej}}(t)$ and $M_{\text{am}}(t) \gg \Delta m$ in this regime. Synchrotron radiation and thermal bremsstrahlung are considered as potential mechanisms of radiative cooling. However, radio observations of TDEs suggest that the synchrotron radio luminosity is negligible compared to the kinetic luminosity, as inferred from equipartition analysis [7, 8]. Similarly, bremsstrahlung cooling is estimated to be inefficient in this regime (see Section IV for details). Neglecting the radiative cooling term, $\dot{E}_C(t)$, on the right-hand side of equation (39) and applying equation (42) to equations (38) and (39) yield the following

simplified equations:

$$M_{\text{am}}(t)\ddot{R}(t) = -\dot{M}_{\text{am}}\dot{R}(t) - \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M_{\text{am}}(t)}{R(t)^2} + \frac{\chi(\gamma-1)}{\xi} \frac{E_{\text{T}}(t)}{R(t)}, \quad (43)$$

$$\dot{E}_{\text{T}}(t) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t)\dot{R}(t)^2 + \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t)}{R(t)} - \frac{\chi(\gamma-1)}{\xi} \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R(t)} E_{\text{T}}(t) \quad (44)$$

at $R(t) \gg r_0$. These two equations can be combined into a single differential equation:

$$\frac{dE_{\text{T}}(t)}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-\frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am}}(t)\dot{R}(t)^2 + \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M_{\text{am}}(t)}{R(t)} \right).$$

This equation is analytically integrable, yielding

$$E_{\text{T}}(t) = -\frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am}}(t)\dot{R}(t)^2 + \frac{GM_{\text{bh}}M_{\text{am}}(t)}{R(t)}, \quad (45)$$

where the integral constant set to zero, as $E_{\text{T}} \rightarrow 0$ and $\dot{R} \rightarrow 0$ at $R \rightarrow \infty$.

We consider the power-law solutions for a set of equations (43) and (44) in the observable region, $R \gg r_0$, as

$$R(t) = R_*\tau^m, \quad (46)$$

where m is the power law index of time, the dimensionless time is introduced as

$$\tau = \frac{t}{t_*},$$

R_* and t_* are the normalization radius and time, respectively. The first and second time derivatives of equation (46), along with the application of equation (46) to equations (17) and (18), yield the following expressions necessary for obtaining the solutions:

$$\dot{R}(t) = V_*\tau^{m-1}, \quad (47)$$

$$\ddot{R}(t) = A_*\tau^{m-2}, \quad (48)$$

$$M_{\text{am}}(t) = M_{\text{am},*} \tau^{3m-sm}, \quad (49)$$

$$\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t) = \dot{M}_{\text{am},*} \tau^{3m-sm-1}, \quad (50)$$

where the coefficients are given by

$$\begin{aligned} V_* &= m \frac{R_*}{t_*}, \\ A_* &= m(m-1) \frac{R_*}{t_*^2}, \\ M_{\text{am},*} &= \frac{4\pi\rho_{\text{am},0}r_0^3}{3-s} \left(\frac{R_*}{r_0} \right)^{3-s}, \\ \dot{M}_{\text{am},*} &= m(3-s) \frac{M_{\text{am},*}}{t_*}. \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

A. Solutions Incorporating Gravity

The objective of this subsection is to determine the power-law index m and the black hole mass M_{bh} using the characteristic quantities R_* and t_* . Substituting equations (46)–(50) into the differential equations (43) and (44), in conjunction with equation (45), leads to:

$$\left[4 - s - \frac{1}{m} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi}\right] \frac{M_{\text{am},*} V_*^2}{R_*} \tau^{4m - sm - 2} = \left[\frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi} - 1\right] \frac{GM_{\text{bh}} M_{\text{am},*}}{R_*^2} \tau^{m - sm},$$

where whether derived from equation (43) or equation (44), the same formula is obtained. This identity holds when the exponents satisfy $4m - sm - 2 = m - sm$, which yields

$$m = \frac{2}{3}.$$

Substituting $m = 2/3$ further provides an expression for the black hole mass:

$$M_{\text{bh}} = K \frac{R_* V_*^2}{G},$$

where the dimensionless coefficient K is given by

$$K = \frac{1}{2} \left[\gamma - 1 + (5 - s) \frac{\xi}{\chi} \right] \left[\gamma - 1 - \frac{\xi}{\chi} \right]^{-1}.$$

This equation imposes the constraint $\xi/\chi < \gamma - 1$; for example, $\xi/\chi < 2/3$ when $\gamma = 5/3$ and $s < 5/2$. In the thin-shell limit, $\xi/\chi \ll 1$, K approaches $1/2$, independently of γ and s .

B. Sedov-Taylor solutions

In this subsection, we derive the Sedov-Taylor solutions. The condition under which the gravitational force is negligible compared to the thermal pressure force in equation (43) is given by $M_{\text{bh}} \ll M_c$, where M_c represents the critical mass at which the thermal pressure force equals the gravitational force. By equating the second and third terms on the right-hand side of equation (43), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} M_c &= \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi} \frac{R_*}{GM_{\text{am},*}} E_{\text{T},*} = \kappa \frac{R_*}{Gm_p} k_{\text{b}} T_{p,*} \\ &\sim 6.2 \times 10^7 M_{\odot} \left(\frac{R_*}{10^{16} \text{ cm}} \right) \left(\frac{T_{p,*}}{10^{10} \text{ K}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

where we assume $\kappa = (3/2)\chi(\gamma - 1)(3 - s) \approx 1$ and $T_{p,*}$ denotes the proton temperature of the shell at R_* , which is assumed to correspond to the downstream temperature in the

non-relativistic strong shock limit. Specifically, we adopt

$$T_{p,*} = \frac{2(\gamma - 1) m_p v_s^2}{(\gamma + 1)^2 k_b} \sim 1.0 \times 10^{10} \text{ K} \left(\frac{v_s}{0.07c} \right)^2, \quad (53)$$

where v_s is the observed shell velocity corresponding to the shock velocity, which is $\sim 0.07c$ for AT2019dsg [7]. For the estimation in equation (52), the thermal energy at R_* is also assumed to be

$$E_{T,*} = 4\pi R_*^2 \Delta R_* \epsilon_{\text{th},*} = \frac{3}{2}(3 - s)\xi M_{\text{am},*} \frac{k_b}{m_p} T_{p,*}, \quad (54)$$

where the thermal energy density is given by $\epsilon_{\text{th},*} = (3/2)(\rho_{\text{am}}(R_*)/m_p)k_b T_{p,*}$ and equation (51) is used for the derivation.

For $M_{\text{bh}} \ll M_c$, equations (43) and (44) are reduced to

$$M_{\text{am}}(t)\ddot{R}(t) = -\dot{M}_{\text{am}}\dot{R} + \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)E_{\text{T}}}{\xi R}, \quad (55)$$

$$\dot{E}_{\text{T}}(t) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t)\dot{R}^2(t) - \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)\dot{R}(t)}{\xi R}E_{\text{T}}, \quad (56)$$

respectively. These two equations are summarized to the single differential equation as

$$\frac{dE_{\text{T}}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-\frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am}}\dot{R}^2 \right).$$

This is analytically integrable as

$$E_{\text{T}} = -\frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am}}\dot{R}^2 + C_0. \quad (57)$$

where C_0 is the integral constant. Substituting equations (46) to (50) into the two differential equations (55) and (56) with equation (57). This operation changes equation (55) as

$$\left[4 - s - \frac{1}{m} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1)}{\xi} \right] \frac{M_{\text{am},*} V_*^2}{R_*} r^{4m - sm - 2} = \frac{\chi(\gamma - 1) C_0}{\xi R_*} r^{-m}.$$

Since this identity holds when $4m - sm - 2 = -m$, we obtain

$$m = \frac{2}{5 - s}.$$

This is the power-law index of the Sedov-Taylor solutions [9, 10]. In this case, the integral constant is calculated to be

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{3 - s}{\gamma - 1} \frac{\xi}{\chi} \right] M_{\text{am},*} V_*^2.$$

Substituting the above equation into equation (57) yields

$$E_T = \frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am}}(V_*^2 - \dot{R}^2) + \frac{1}{2}\frac{3-s}{\gamma-1}\frac{\xi}{\chi}M_{\text{am},*}V_*^2.$$

Since $\dot{R} = V_*$ at R_* , we obtain $E_{T,*}$ as

$$E_{T,*} = \frac{1}{2}\frac{3-s}{\gamma-1}\frac{\xi}{\chi}M_{\text{am},*}V_*^2. \quad (58)$$

On the other hand, combining equation (54) with equations (51) and (53) yields

$$E_{T,*} = 3\frac{(3-s)(\gamma-1)}{(\gamma+1)^2}\xi M_{\text{am},*}v_s^2. \quad (59)$$

Equating equation (58) with equation (59) expresses the shock velocity using V_* as

$$v_s^2 = \frac{1}{6}\frac{1}{\chi}\frac{(\gamma+1)^2}{(\gamma-1)^2}V_*^2.$$

C. Momentum-driven Snowplow Solutions

If the kinetic energy of the ambient matter is much larger than the thermal energy at $R_* \gg r_0$, equations (55) and (56) are, furthermore, reduced to

$$M_{\text{am}}(t)\ddot{R}(t) = -\dot{M}_{\text{am}}\dot{R}, \quad (60)$$

$$\dot{E}_T(t) = \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\text{am}}(t)\dot{R}^2(t). \quad (61)$$

These two equations are summarized to one differential equation as

$$\frac{dE_T}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}\left(-\frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am}}\dot{R}^2\right).$$

This is analytically integrable as

$$E_T = -\frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am}}\dot{R}^2 + C_1, \quad (62)$$

where C_1 is the integral constant. Now, E_T goes to zero at R_* because the thermal energy is, by definition, negligibly smaller than the kinetic energy of the shell. The integral constant results in

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{2}M_{\text{am},*}V_*^2.$$

Substituting equations (46)–(50) into the differential equations (60) and (61), together with equation (62), modifies equation (60) as

$$\left[\frac{1}{m} - 1\right]\frac{M_{\text{am},*}V_*^2}{R_*}\tau^{4m-sm-2} = (3-s)\frac{M_{\text{am},*}V_*^2}{R_*}\tau^{4m-sm-2}.$$

This identity leads to the following relation for m :

$$m = \frac{1}{4 - s}.$$

The solution characterized by this power-law index is referred to as the momentum-driven snowplow solutions. This result corresponds to the one derived in the TDE context by Hayasaki & Yamazaki (2023) [1].

III. OBSERVATIONAL CONSTRAINTS ON SHELL PARAMETERS

A. Relation Between v_s and V_*

Radio monitoring provides the average expansion speed by fitting broadband synchrotron spectra with an equipartition SED model. Our analytic framework instead requires the instantaneous shock speed $v_s = \dot{R}(t_*)$. For non-relativistic, nearly spherical shells this distinction is minor: the shell decelerates only slightly between epochs, and projection effects change the velocity by at most a few tens of per cent. Consequently, v_s and V_* differ by no more than a factor of two, matching the factor-few radius–magnetic-field degeneracy reported by Alexander et al. (2020) [11]. We fold this systematic error into the \mathcal{D}_c values listed below.

B. Observed Shell Parameters and Corresponding \mathcal{D}_c Values

Our dynamical framework targets the early-to-intermediate phase of shell evolution, corresponding to the early rising and peak stages of the radio light curve. ($\lesssim 300$ d after optical discovery). For six well-studied, non-jetted TDEs we quote the shell radius R_* , expansion velocity V_* , and SMBH mass M_\bullet reported in the literature and set $v_s = V_*$ in equation (26) of the main text to obtain

$$\mathcal{D}_c = \frac{(\gamma + 1)^2}{2\kappa(\gamma - 1)} \frac{GM_\bullet}{R_*V_*^2}. \quad (63)$$

When $\mathcal{D}_c \ll 1$, the Sedov–Taylor solution governs the shell dynamics and equation (23) of the main text is not applicable. Conversely, the gravity-dominated $m = 2/3$ solution applies only when $\mathcal{D}_c > 1$, while $0.5 \lesssim \mathcal{D}_c \lesssim 1$ defines a transition regime in which both scalings coexist. In the following calculations, $\kappa = 1$ (see equation 52) and $\gamma = 5/3$ are applied.

Table I lists the results. The six events span $0.002 \leq \mathcal{D}_c \leq 0.84$, all below the gravity-dominated threshold $\mathcal{D}_c = 1$. Four of them—ASASSN-14li, AT2019dsg, AT2019azh, and AT2020opy—have $\mathcal{D}_c \lesssim 0.06$ and therefore reside deep in the Sedov–Taylor phase. AT2020vwl ($\mathcal{D}_c = 0.18$) and eRASSt J2344 ($\mathcal{D}_c = 0.84$) occupy intermediate values, with the latter lying closest to the transition and thus providing the first observational hint of the onset of gravity domination. The existence of such intermediate cases suggests that future surveys may discover TDEs with $\mathcal{D}_c > 1$; these would lie firmly in the $m = 2/3$ regime and

allow the SMBH mass to be inferred directly from radio-measured shell dynamics.

TABLE I. Shell parameters obtained from equipartition modelling of broadband synchrotron spectra. Column (1) Event name. (2) Observing epoch in days since optical discovery. (3) Shell radius R_* . (4) Mean expansion speed V_* . (5) Observed SMBH mass M_\bullet . (6) Dimensionless parameter \mathcal{D}_c defined in equation (63). (7) Original references for the radio data and the adopted M_\bullet values.

Event	Epoch	R_*	V_*	M_\bullet	\mathcal{D}_c	Reference
	(d)	(cm)	(cm s^{-1})	(M_\odot)		
ASASSN-14li	143	1.5×10^{16}	1.2×10^9	1.0×10^6	0.03	Alexander et al. (2016) [12]
AT2019dsg	130	2.0×10^{16}	1.8×10^9	5.0×10^6	0.06	Cendes et al. (2021) [13]
AT2019azh	183	6.3×10^{16}	4.0×10^9	3.0×10^6	0.002	Goodwin et al. (2022) [14]
AT2020opy	180	5.0×10^{16}	1.6×10^9	2.5×10^6	0.03	Goodwin et al. (2023a) [15]
AT2020vwl	142	1.3×10^{16}	1.1×10^9	3.6×10^6	0.18	Goodwin et al. (2023b) [16]
eRASSt J2344	214	2.6×10^{16}	1.4×10^9	6.3×10^7	0.84	Goodwin et al. (2024) [17]

IV. COOLING BY THERMAL BREMSSTRAHLUNG

In this subsection, we estimate the cooling rate due to the thermal bremsstrahlung. For simplicity, we assume the electron number density n_e equals the proton number density $n_p = \rho_{\text{am}}(R)/m_p$ in the shell. In the numerical estimates presented in the following equations, we set $s = 2$ unless stated otherwise. The electron number density at $R = R_*$ is then given by using equation (14) as

$$n_e = n_0 \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{-s}, \quad (64)$$

where n_0 is the normalization of the density and is estimated as $n_0 = n_*(R_*/r_0)^s \sim 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ by using $n_* = 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $R_* = 10^{16} \text{ cm}$, which are values close to the observed ones [7]. We also designate r_0 as $r_t = (M_{\text{bh}}/m_*)^{1/3} r_*$ [18], which is the tidal disruption radius corresponding to an SMBH with $10^{6.7} M_\odot$ and a solar-type star:

$$r_0 \sim 1.2 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm} \left(\frac{M}{10^{6.7} M_\odot} \right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{m_*}{M_\odot} \right)^{-1/3} \left(\frac{r_*}{R_\odot} \right). \quad (65)$$

The optical depth of the thin shell at R_* is approximated to be

$$\begin{aligned}\tau &= n_e \sigma_T \Delta R \\ &\sim 0.01 \left(\frac{\xi}{0.1} \right) \left(\frac{n_0}{10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}} \right) \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{1-s},\end{aligned}$$

where equations (28), (64), and (65) were used for the estimation. This equation demonstrates that the shell is optically thin for $R(t) \geq r_0$ as long as $s \geq 1$ and is thus much thinner at $R(t) = R_*$.

Next, let us whether the thermal energy is lost by free-free emissions in a reasonable time. The emissivity of the thermal bremsstrahlung is given by [19] as

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_\nu^{\text{ff}} &= \frac{2^5 \pi e^6}{3 m_e c^3} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{3 k_B m_e}} T_e^{-1/2} n_e^2 e^{-h\nu/k_B T_e} \bar{g}_{\text{ff}} \\ &\sim 4.1 \times 10^{-21} \left(\frac{T_e}{10^7 \text{ K}} \right)^{-1/2} \left(\frac{n_0}{10^{10} \text{ cm}^3} \right)^2 \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{-2s} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\text{ff}}}{1.0} \right) \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ Hz}^{-1},\end{aligned}\quad (66)$$

where e is an elementary charge, m_e is the electron mass, \bar{g}_{ff} is the Gaunt factor, T_e is the electron temperature of the thin shell, which is assumed to be $\sim 10^7 \text{ K}$, and the exponential term $\exp(-h\nu/k_B T_e)$ is also assumed to be unity. The cooling function is given by [19] as

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda_{\text{ff}} &= \int_0^\infty \epsilon_\nu^{\text{ff}} d\nu \\ &\sim 8.6 \times 10^{-4} \left(\frac{T_e}{10^7 \text{ K}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{n_0}{10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{-2s} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\text{ff}}}{1.0} \right) \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-3},\end{aligned}$$

where equation (66) was used for the derivation. The cooling timescale is then given by

$$\begin{aligned}t_{\text{cool}} &= \frac{\epsilon_{\text{th},e}}{\Lambda_{\text{ff}}} \\ &\sim 3.3 \times 10^4 \text{ s} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\text{ff}}}{1.0} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{T_e}{10^7 \text{ K}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{n_0}{10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^s,\end{aligned}$$

where $\epsilon_{\text{th},e} = (3/2)n_e k_B T_e$ is the thermal energy density of the electrons in the shell. This equation indicates that $t_{\text{cool}} \sim 10^{10} \text{ s}$ is significantly longer than the dynamical time, $t_{\text{dyn}} = R_*/v_s \sim 10^6 \text{ s}$, when $R(t) = R_*$.

The energy loss rate of thermal bremsstrahlung is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{E}_{\text{brems}} &= \int_V \Lambda_{\text{ff}} dV \\ &\sim 1.8 \times 10^{36} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\text{ff}}}{1.0} \right) \left(\frac{\xi}{0.1} \right) \left(\frac{T_e}{10^7 \text{ K}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{n_0}{10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{R(t)}{r_0} \right)^{3-2s} \text{ erg s}^{-1}.\end{aligned}$$

The energy loss rate decreases with the shell radius as long as $s > 3/2$. Since the thermal energy E_T at R_* is roughly estimated by using equation (54) to be $E_{T,*} = 4\pi R_* \Delta R_* \epsilon_{th,*} \sim 2.8 \times 10^{49}$ erg for the appropriate values and parameters, the cooling energy lost over the dynamical time is too small to affect the shell dynamics.

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